

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA

Full resource

Table of contents

Introduction	2
Summary.....	2
Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework.....	2
Common obstacles in implementing RRA	3
Obstacles identified in the GraspOS Surveys	3
Obstacles identified by other actors.....	4
Actions for overcoming common obstacles	5
Policy collaboration	7
Supporting initiatives.....	7
Investment in assessment data infrastructure.....	8
GraspOS solutions.....	9
Strategy for culture change	10
CoARA's Reform journey	10
References and further resources	11

Introduction

Summary

Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA introduces the common obstacles identified, e.g., in the GraspOS Surveys (Hyrkkänen et al. 2023) and suggests actions to overcome these obstacles. The two surveys conducted for the landscape analysis show that the situation and challenges of the nine GraspOS pilots regarding CoARA Agreement and assessment practices are indeed very similar compared to the 54 landscape survey participants from 19 European countries. Based on these survey results it is now possible to identify guidelines to overcome common obstacles (Tatum et al. 2024).

The obstacles identified are presented by a category (practical, policy related or culture related). The most frequently mentioned barrier mentioned in the surveys was the complexity of reform due for example to different national and disciplinary practices, and the second most frequent barrier was concerns over costs, for example in terms of skilled staff and support structures. There were also concerns about resistance from researchers, limited awareness of the reform and lack of evidence on its potential benefits. Other actors have identified very similar obstacles.

The guide suggests actions for overcoming common obstacles of different categories. These include, e.g., actions for policy collaboration and investment in infrastructure.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports identifying and overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA.

[SCOPE framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Common obstacles in implementing RRA

Obstacles identified in the GraspOS Surveys

Two surveys were conducted during 2023 by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV):

- 1) GraspOS landscape survey for pilots and
- 2) GraspOS landscape survey on Reforming Research Assessment (Hyrkkänen et al. 2023).

The GraspOS landscape survey on Reforming Research Assessment was launched in May 2023 on the GraspOS website. The purpose of the survey was to gain overview of the state-of-the-art research assessment practices at the research performing and funding organisations, and other organisations involved with research assessment. A total of 54 full submitted responses were received. In addition, all nine (9) participating pilots involved in the project, who represent a highly diverse group of stakeholders, provided responses to the questions in the GraspOS landscape survey. For full description of methods and results please see Hyrkkänen et al. (2023).

Based on Hyrkkänen et al. (2023), the most frequently mentioned barrier to reform of research assessment (61.1% of the respondents) was the **complexity of reform due for example to different national and disciplinary practices** (see table 1).

The second most frequent barrier (46.3%) was constituted by **concerns over costs**, for example in terms of skilled staff and support structures. These were the top barriers among both 38 CoARA signatories, as well as 16 respondent organisations that indicated not having yet signed the Agreement. Especially signatories were concerned about resistance from researchers, limited awareness of the reform and lack of evidence on its potential benefits, while implementation problems are relatively important to non-signatories.

Table 1. Common obstacles identified in the GraspOS Surveys (Hyrkkänen et al. 2023) divided into three categories (policy related, practical, culture related).

Obstacle	Frequency	Type
Complexity of research assessment reform (e.g., different national and disciplinary practices)	61.1 %	Policy related

Concerns over increased costs (e.g., skilled staff, support structures)	46.3 %	Practical
Resistance to research assessment reform from researchers	38.9 %	Culture related
Limited awareness of the reform and lack of evidence on its potential benefits	37 %	Culture related
Lack of evidence on potential benefits of research assessment reform	35.2 %	Culture related
Alignment of institutional assessment procedures with nationally and internationally dominant procedures	35.2 %	Policy related
Absence of incentivising policies or guidelines from external actors (e.g., national/regional governments, research funding organisations)	31.5 %	Policy related
Implementation problems	29.6 %	Practical
Lack of institutional capacity (e.g., skilled staff, support structures)	27.8 %	Practical
Lack of suitable data or metrics	24.1 %	Practical
Lack of coordination among the relevant actors within the institution	24.1 %	Practical
Resistance to research assessment reform from academic leadership	20.4 %	Culture related
Lack of institutional autonomy due to national/regional rules and regulations	18.5 %	Policy related
Lack of institutional autonomy due to rules and regulations imposed by research funding organisation	14.8 %	Policy related

Obstacles identified by other actors

For comparison, there have also been other actors who have conducted work in identifying obstacles in implementing RRA and found very similar types of issues. For example, **Mustajoki et al. (2021)** identified the following points as main obstacles:

- Cost in developing infrastructure (practical)
- Lack of resources for qualitative assessment (practical)
- Limitations in expertise in responsible assessment (practical)
- Inconsistencies in policies to regulate open science, data management and assessments (policy related)
- Cultural and practical investment in the current assessment and evaluation system (Culture and policy related)

Similarly, [DORA Case study of Responsible Research Network, Finland](#) (DORA 2020) highlighted as specific obstacles faced the following:

- lack of evidence on potential benefits of research assessment reform (culture related)
- resistance to research assessment reform from researchers (culture related)
- concerns over increased costs (practical)
- complexity of research assessment reform (practical)
- lack of coordination among the relevant actors within the institution (practical)
- lack of reliable data sources for assessment (practical)

The CoARA Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment (WG ACA) has developed a targeted mapping of initiatives on academic career assessment, which included a survey and case studies on academic career assessment initiatives (CoARA Working Group ACA 2024).

The survey gathered information on institutional/organisational level initiatives that aim to broaden the criteria and methods for evaluating the outputs and impacts of academic activities for the purposes of recruitment, performance evaluation and career progression of academic staff. The survey was addressed to higher education and research organisations worldwide. It targeted organisations that were planning, initiating or implementing a reform process on academic career assessment - either at departmental/unit level or organisational level.

The results of the survey included 236 valid responses, from 41 countries ([CoARA Working Group ACA 2024](#)). The following were named as reasons for not being involved in reform or as challenges for assessment reform by the respondents:

- National regulations (institutions have limited autonomy in the definition of ACA reforms) (policy related)
- Resource and capacity constraints (e.g. limited time, staff, and resources and organisational capacity to implement reforms) (practical)
- Recent reforms implemented (organisations prefer to evaluate the current system's effectiveness before considering further reforms) (practical & culture related)
- Current system is satisfactory (culture related)
- Resistance to change (culture related)
- Other (e.g. merger processes ongoing, following rules of parent organisation)

Please see CoARA Working Group ACA (2024) for more details.

Actions for overcoming common obstacles

As stated by Mustajoki et al. (2021), if creating a responsible assessment culture “*was easy, it would have been done already*”. The changes in assessment culture meet challenges, which must be overcome. Awareness of barriers supports developing a roadmap from vision to reality. Given the scale of these challenges, a multi-stakeholder program - including government agencies, research funding and performing organisations, open science and research assessment and management

communities, public and commercial service providers - is critical to achieve a shared global view (Mustajoki et al. 2021).

As priorities for action, Mustajoki et al. (2021) call for

1. policy collaboration and
2. investment in assessment data infrastructure (see below for more details).

Table 2. Summary table (inspired by Nosek 2019, see below for more details) of suggested actions for overcoming different types of RRA obstacles (inspired by e.g., Mustajoki et al. 2021, CoARA 2022, CoARA Working Group ACA 2024, see below for more details) with examples of initiatives and good practices.

Action	Policy	Practical	Culture
	Make it required and aligned	Make it possible and easy	Make it normative and rewarding
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop, join and support national and international coalitions for responsible research assessment (e.g., CoARA) • Strengthen guidance to translate principles into institutional policies and practices • Call for more responsible assessment practices • Combine efforts • Create a shared vision • Align policies and practices with an institution's mission • Align policies with reform initiatives at national and international level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop, use, share and promote new (open) tools, platforms and technologies of assessment and evaluation • Experiment, evaluate and amplify what works • Share experiences and knowledge • Call for investment in assessment data infrastructure • Promote dialogue between professionals, including open science and evaluation experts, researchers, data stewards and research software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use assessment models that consider broader activities • Recognize collaborative contributions (teamwork) • Raise awareness • Engage relevant stakeholders (e.g., researchers) in the process, also in early-stage planning and discussion • Find conceptual clarity in hiring, promotion, and tenure policies • Communicate the vision on campus and externally • Lead with example • Reflect on change process • Implement innovative

		engineers to support development of assessment infrastructure	assessment schemes and career models
Examples of good practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible Research Network, Finland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Recognition & Rewards Programme, Netherlands

Policy collaboration

Based on Mustajoki et al. (2021), there is a need for a global and shared vision for assessment. Shared vision will benefit all stakeholders. The range of guidelines and policies which have been developed to encourage and regulate open science, data management and assessment at different levels rarely align with each other, making it difficult for researchers and institutions to know which policy to follow when (Mustajoki et al. 2021).

Since research is international and researchers move between institutions and countries, the actions taken in RRA should have a global scale. However, as “one size does not fit all”, there is also a need for flexibility. Indeed, Stroobants (2024) calls for reforms that are “*as aligned as possible, but as diverse as necessary*” and suggests more efforts to frame and align reform movements around RRA principles.

Supporting initiatives

Joining and supporting relevant initiatives is an effective way to advance RRA reform by working towards policy collaboration on a global scale. Below are the descriptions of the most relevant ones.

The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)

In 2012, a group of editors and publishers of scholarly journals meeting in the Annual Meeting of The American Society for Cell Biology in San Francisco, developed a set of recommendations known as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA 2012). Nowadays DORA is a worldwide initiative: over 22,000 individuals and over 3000 organizations in 166 countries have signed DORA (in December 2024). DORA’s mission is to advance practical and robust approaches to research assessment globally and across all scholarly disciplines.

DORA consists of 18 recommendations that are aimed at funding agencies, academic institutions, journals and organizations that supply metrics, and also at individual researchers.

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA)

[The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated. The vision of CoARA is “*to recognise the diverse outputs, practices,*

and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research through an emphasis on qualitative judgement in assessment, for which peer review is essential, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators”.

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA, CoARA 2022) encompasses many of the ambitions of earlier declarations and expands upon them by requiring institutions to commit to actually changing their practice within an agreed timeframe. Joining the coalition is possible either as a signatory of the Agreement or as a full member of CoARA. As of 14 February 2025, 825 organisations have signed the agreement.

Signatories commit to a common vision, which is that *“the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators”* (CoARA 2022).

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information

The signatories of [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) (2025) commit to taking a lead in transforming the way research information is used and produced. Openness of information about the conduct and communication of research must be the new norm. Barcelona Declaration is important for RRA, because fair assessment of researchers and institutions requires full transparency.

cOAlition S

Funders have an essential role to play in shaping research culture. cOAlition S, an initiative for funders to make full and immediate Open Access to research publications a reality. It is built around Plan S, which consists of one target and 10 principles (cOAlition S 2025).

cOAlition S is committed to fostering responsible and fair approaches to research assessment. This intention is set out in the Plan S principles: *“when assessing research outputs during funding decisions, cOAlition S funders will make decisions based on the intrinsic merit of the work and not the publication channel, its impact factor (or other journal-level metrics), or the publisher”*.

Investment in assessment data infrastructure

Mustajoki et al. (2021) also highlights the importance of investment in assessment data infrastructure. The research communities require new infrastructures for gathering, storing and sharing assessment data at institutional, national and international level.

Balancing the use of metrics and qualitative assessments is also a question of wise use of resources. Mustajoki et al. (2021) suggest that *“the experts’ work can also be facilitated by producing good and reliable data to support qualitative evaluations, for example by developing infrastructure and services for the production, use, storing and sharing of structured and guided narrative descriptions and case reports. By making expert assessments more open (e.g., open peer review), the outcomes of an assessment can be used more than once. The experts’ workload in peer review needs to be*

balanced with merit and rewards for peer review work. Ideally, performing assessments should be integrated in a natural way in the process of doing research.”

Priorities for assessment infrastructure investments according to Mustajoki et al. (2021):

- **International funding call** by EOSC, or other similar organisation, to begin developing the technical solution for shared assessment infrastructure and required data models
- Building an **assessment infrastructure with mutually shared architecture** supporting quantitative and qualitative assessment information, which
 - Has shared data models and PIDs
 - Builds on existing infrastructures
 - Provides different levels of access for different types of users
 - Incorporates consent from researchers
 - Minimises assessment data re-entry and maximises assessment data reuse
- Establishing an **international forum for dialogue** between professionals, including open science and evaluation experts, researchers, data stewards and research software engineers to support development of assessment infrastructure.

GraspOS solutions

Infrastructure

GraspOS aims to address the challenges of RRA by designing and delivering an [Open and Federated Research Assessment Infrastructure](#) (formerly known as “Federated Open Metrics Infrastructure - FOMI”). This infrastructure paves the way for the creation of an Open Research Assessment Dataspace (ORAD) by aggregating open resources (e.g., next-generation metrics and indicators, data, tools, services, and guidance offered by different sources) that can catalyse the implementation of policy reforms towards an OS-aware RRA framework.

Case studies

[GraspOS pilots](#) represent three types of Open Science enabled research assessment:

1. funding agencies and national stakeholders who are operating infrastructure and use for evaluation of funding
2. universities, including departments and research groups, interested in recruiting and assessment, and
3. thematic disciplines who can set general assessment criteria based on infrastructure and discipline needs.

One of the central results of the pilots’ work (Himanen 2025) show that

- **community involvement is key** to make sure that
 - the **resources, tools and services** developed to support responsible research assessment are relevant and useful
 - they **ease the evaluation work** for both targets of evaluations as well as evaluators
 - **all relevant stakeholders** for each evaluation event **have a mutual understanding** of what is being evaluated and why.

Strategy for culture change

The "**Strategy for Culture Change**" (Nosek 2019) is a framework, often presented as a pyramid, that outlines a progressive approach to changing the culture of a community, particularly in research and publishing. It suggests that culture change requires building infrastructure, then experience, reward systems, and ultimately policy.

Figure 2. Pyramid for the strategy for culture change (Nosek 2019).

Nosek (2019) defines that “*infrastructure is the base of the pyramid making behaviour change possible*” and continues: “*The infrastructure at the base of our culture change pyramid is reinforced by addressing norms, incentives, and policies. For shifting norms, we are trying to make the desired behaviours visible*”.

CoARA’s Reform journey

Below are the steps from the “Reform journey: a suggested process for achieving the Commitments” (CoARA 2022, Annex 3).

“The reform journey sets out a suggested, non-prescriptive step-by-step process to help organisations achieve the Commitments. This journey is presented as chronological steps; however, the change process will probably not be chronological, and organisations can adapt the journey and start from the step they deem most appropriate for their context.”

1. **Allocate resources**, whether in terms of capacity or budget, to actively engage in the reform journey
2. **Communicate your intention to reform**, explain how you have started the process of reviewing or developing criteria, tools and processes in line with the core commitment

3. **Evaluate current assessment practices** in terms of alignment with the Principles and Commitments, consider also what currently works well and how this can be retained in parallel to any new practice - Re-evaluate at fixed intervals, whenever broad reforms to assessments are implemented, or when problems are identified
4. **Engage those being assessed** in the development and design of assessment criteria and processes, work with researchers to enable consideration of differences between disciplines and career levels
5. **Develop existing and design new assessment criteria**, tools, and processes with assessors and those that are assessed; consider the diversity of contributions including: diverse outputs beyond journal publications and in different languages; diverse practices including those that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and inclusiveness of research and the research process including peer review, teamwork and collaboration; and diverse activities including teaching, leadership, supervision, training, and mentoring, according to the nature of each research discipline
6. **Interrogate developed and new approaches** by working with assessors and those that are assessed (e.g. who might new approaches discriminate against; how might they be gamed; what are the potential unintended consequences)
7. **Implement developed and new assessment criteria**, tools, and processes according to the Principles and Commitments; consider awareness raising, rewards, policies, training, infrastructure, and capacity building and include data collection to support monitoring, evaluation and mutual learning
8. **Evaluate developed and new assessment criteria**, tools, and processes
9. **Share data / information, participate in mutual learning** within and beyond the Coalition, supported by mechanisms developed by the Coalition
10. **Coordinate with other organisations** at national and international level, and promote international coordination and harmonisation
11. **Continue to evolve assessment criteria**, tools, and processes based on learning from own evaluations and those of others

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